

INTERPRETATION OF THE IMAGE OF AN ORIENTAL MAN IN THE POEMS OF A. AKHMATOVA

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Annotation In this article, the author analyzed Akhmatova's poems, the East is mythologized through the images of an oriental person ("little lamb", "mother", "friends", "Khalims meet nightingale singing", "Tamerlane", "Scheherazade", etc.), while attract authentic material: linguistic and literary facts, identified realities of the Uzbek landscape, identified quotes from oriental poetry that are not obvious to the Russian language.

Key words: non-fictional East, oriental motif, man of the East. Means of expression: metaphor, comparison.

Introduction

As Likhachev notes, only in the 18th century did Russian culture discover the East with all its traditions, and since that time, the early negative view has been replaced by a positive one. The East was the focus of attention of many creators of the "Silver Age" and for them it was the country of Sufi poets: from Gafiz to Rumi. And Akhmatova in her work often refers to the image of the East. The theme of the East dominates in many poems. She tries to describe the East as widely and variously as possible, as it really is. This process is carried out against the background of biographical subtext, and against the background of individual images, and in her translation line.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The purpose of the work is to identify and describe the Oriental man in Akhmatova's poems

To achieve the goal, the following tasks are solved in the work:

- 1) commenting on eastern (Uzbek) realities in Akhmatova's poems;
- 3) consideration of allusions to an oriental person in Akhmatova's poems, correlation of oriental images in Akhmatova's lyrics with ancient mythological plots and images;
- 4) identification of the eastern picture of the world in Akhmatova's poems;

Research methods: theoretical, historical-literary, ideological-aesthetic, biographical- chronological, elements of contextual analysis.

results

In many of Akhmatova's poems, which were written in Tashkent, the image of a man of the East and names (Chusti, Aibek, Gulyam, Halima) are often found, which became one of the means of Akhmatova's interpretation of the image of the East.

The war has never spared anyone. She also took everything from Akhmatova, but she was unable to take away from her one thing – the most precious thing in a person – her own dignity, spirit, a verbal pearl. Akhmatova's poems made people happy, restored their lost hope, taught them to resist evil and untruth. All these traits of a person with a steely character made her spiritually rich.

Akhmatova, who lived in Tashkent, in a certain period of time, left her unforgettable traces both on the land of Tashkent and in the souls of "Asians".

Akhmatova was a favorite of the public. Therefore, the government also took care of her health and condition. The then secretary of the Writers' Union of Uzbekistan, poet Hamid Alimjan, helped her a lot, who called her poem "Courage" a masterpiece of Russian military lyrics.

In the poem "Now I thank everyone" (1945) Akhmatova mentions the names of some Uzbek poets:

Rakhmat and Khayer.

And I'm waving a handkerchief at you.

Rakhmat, Aibek, rakhmat, Chusti,

Rakhmat, Tashkent! – I'm sorry, I'm sorry...

My quiet, ancient home.

Rahmat and stars, and flowers

And little sheep

Black - haired mothers

On young hands... [Akhmatova, 1999, vol. 2, book 1, p. 96].

In a poem dedicated to the entire Uzbek people, Akhmatova addresses the words "Rakhmat" ("thank you") and "Hyer" ("goodbye"). "Ancient House" – here the emphasis is on the fact that she feels at home in Tashkent, for her this is her native space.

"Little Baranchuk" – Uzbek language belongs to the group of Turkic languages of the Altai language family. Since Uzbek and Tatar belong to the same language family, some words have become common. Including the word "baranchuk". "Baranchuk" is a Tatar word meaning a baby ram (the Uzbek equivalent is "Kyzichok" – lamb). In the Uzbek people, a sheep (or lamb) is a symbol of helplessness. An example of this is this Uzbek proverb: "Kyı ogzidan chyp olmagan" – soft, gentle, helpless. Since the child is as helpless as a lamb, Uzbek mothers call their children lambs. Therefore, Akhmatova uses the word "baranchuk" in her lines. The image of a lamb child is present in Akhmatova's translated poem "You are not an orphan" by the Uzbek poet G. Gulyam, whom she considered one of the best poets of Asia:

Are you an orphan?.. Calm down, dear!

Like a kind sun bending over you,

Full of maternal, deep love,

A big country protects your childhood.

If your father has died, be strong, do not grieve.

Go to sleep, my boy, my white lamb, go to sleep.

I am the father! I'll give you anything you want,

All your cares will become my happiness

[cit. according to Nikolenko, Letters about Tashkent].

Akhmatova mythologizes the image of the East in the poem "I haven't been here for seven hundred years" (1944):

I haven't been here for seven hundred years,
But nothing has changed...
God's mercy is still pouring out
From unquestionable heights,
And the same song the mother sings.
It is solid my Asian home
I'll be back. Bloom, fence,
Be full, clean pond...

[Akhmatova, 1999, vol. 2., book 1, p. 265].

The reference to seven hundred years emphasizes that Akhmatova considers the East to be her homeland, where she returned. Akhmatova is not interested in statistics, but in the history and culture of the East: if we go back 7 centuries ago, we find ourselves in the 13th century – the heyday of Persian-Tajik culture, represented by Saadi, Rumi, Hafiz. And here the theme of a large and ancient house of all mankind sounds like a call to preserve this house for the sake and for the good of the future. Why does she want to cover an entire epoch with her eyes?! It's not a matter of some artistic technique here, the mystery of recognizing something in the ancient East is striking, something native and close. Akhmatova assures that Asian mercy, generosity, good nature and mercy are not something fleeting in an Asian house, so the author firmly declares that "it is durable."

What is the meaning of the expression "mother sings a song"? When spring comes and apricots bloom, all the peoples of the East celebrate the spring holiday "Navruz" on March 21. On this day, all the women gather and perform various performances, and, of course, "alla" (lullaby) is sung.

"I will come again" – having visited the "ancient house", Akhmatova wants to say: "If I rise again, I will rise not in the West, but in the East and will stay in it forever!" Therefore, she promises to come to this house again. She blesses the East from the

bottom of her heart, wishes it to continue to exist: "Bloom, fence, be full, clean pond!"

The image of the East is given in the poem "Have I become completely different" (1944):

On this ancient dry land

I'm home again.

I know there are friends around –

There are millions of them

[Akhmatova, 1998, vol.2, book 1, p. 62].

Akhmatova was friends with representatives of the literary circle of other nationalities – with Aibek, Gulyam, Chusti, Kahhar, Halima. The proof of this is the poem "Everything will come back to me again" (1943):

Everything will come back to me again:

A hot night and languor

(As if Asia is delirious in a dream),

Halim nightingale singing,

And the biblical daffodils bloom,

And an invisible blessing

A breeze rustles across the country

[Akhmatova, 1998, vol. 2, book 1, p. 56].

"Halima nightingale singing" – the image of Halima is taken from real life. Akhmatova loved and appreciated literature, culture, and art of other nations with dignity. Akhmatova was fascinated by the work of the famous Persian poet-thinker Lutfi, whose gazelles she skillfully translated into Russian, which she mentions in the poem "Another lyrical digression" (1943):

And I have to translate Lutfi

Under the fire-breathing sunset

[Akhmatova, 1998, vol.2, book 1, p. 51].

Halima Nasyrova is a famous Uzbek singer who sang songs on the Lutfi gazelle, so Akhmatova communicated with her. "Nightingale singing" – in the East, masters whose work deserves the respect of the people are usually called "nightingale", whose voice is loved by everyone and recognized by everyone.

In the poem "To fall asleep upset" (1943) Akhmatova writes:

Scheherazade

Coming from the garden...

so that's what you are, the East!

[Akhmatova, 1999, book 2, p. 423].

Scheherazade is the heroine of the fairy tales "One Thousand and One Nights". This poem is dedicated to Galina Gerus (Kozlovskaya), who in 1937 was exiled to Tashkent together with her husband, the Leningrad composer A. F. Kozlovsky. In Tashkent, they were close friends of Akhmatova. G. L. Kozlovskaya tells the background of this poem: "my husband often took her for a walk in the old city, which he knew and loved. He somehow brought her to the "paradise" in which our three years of exile were lived. Two houses, two gardens with cherries and peaches that bloomed and then bore fruit, a silvery fragrant djida, a huge poplar and an apricot tree that covered half of the garden. There was everything: a vine, a rose bush, and a ditch running along the paths, where fragrant mint curls in all colors. Everything is clean, everything is watered, everything is swept. As always, they were greeted by two girls with lots of pigtails. Under their joyful cries, a samovar boiled and a dastarkhan appeared -a treat: raisins and dried apricots... That evening Alexey Fedorovich showed his pictures of the days when we lived there on Igarchi Saddlers Street. Anna Andreevna recognized the brazier in the corner, and the poplar, and me standing with a jug. Three days later she brought me a piece of poetry. She gave it to me and kissed me. The piece of paper says "Galina Gerus" [Kozlovskaya]. The appearance of the fabulous oriental character Scheherazade is explained by the fact that Akhmatova called Galina Gerus "my Scheherazade". Through oriental dance, Akhmatova introduces the reader to her "ancient home – Asia".

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Akhmatova's Tashkent poems contain: oriental motif, oriental philosophy, description of oriental nature and culture – all this brings Akhmatova's lyrics so close to the poetry of the East that the reader (who does not know that their author is Akhmatova) may think that such expressions as "eternal roses", "my ancient house", "the all-knowing mouth", "mangalochy courtyard", "high poplar", "red poppy", "baranchuk" belong not to a Russian, but to an oriental poet.

Thus, this mythologization of the East in several dimensions (nature, man, history, way of life, traditions, language, translator's experience) Akhmatova holistically and broadly portray the East as "the cradle of humanity", "the cradle of civilization". Love for someone else's culture becomes the basis for the manifestation of love for one's own culture and for the whole world.

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